

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№2(2)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 454 sahifa,
2-fevral, 2026-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi"
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

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Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
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reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
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Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

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DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES THROUGH THE USE OF SPECIAL PHYSICAL EXERCISES WITH STUDENT PARTICIPATION

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations for developing students' physical qualities through the use of special physical exercises. The features of developing strength, endurance, speed, flexibility, and coordination abilities within the educational process of a higher education institution are outlined. The principles of structuring classes, load dosage, and pedagogical control are analyzed. The necessity of the systematic application of special exercises as an effective means of strengthening health, increasing work capacity, and fostering stable motivation for physical education is substantiated.

Key words: physical qualities, special exercises, students, physical education, strength, endurance, flexibility, coordination, educational process.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada maxsus jismoniy mashqlar yordamida talabalarning jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirishning nazariy va uslubiy asoslari ko'rib chiqilgan. Oliy ta'lim muassasasidagi o'quv jarayoni doirasida kuch, chidamlilik, tezkorlik, egiluvchanlik va muvofiqlashtirish (koordinatsiya) qobiliyatlarini shakllantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari yoritilgan. Mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish tamoyillari, yuklamalarni me'yorlash va pedagogik nazorat masalalari tahlil qilingan. Salomatlikni mustahkamlash, ish qobiliyatini oshirish hamda jismoniy tarbiya bilan shug'ullanishga nisbatan barqaror motivatsiyani shakllantirishning samarali vositasi sifatida maxsus mashqlarni tizimli ravishda qo'llash zarurati asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy sifatlar, maxsus mashqlar, talabalar, jismoniy tarbiya, kuch, chidamlilik, egiluvchanlik, muvofiqlashtirish, o'quv jarayoni.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются теоретические и методические основы развития физических качеств студентов с использованием специальных физических упражнений. Раскрываются особенности формирования силы, выносливости, быстроты, гибкости и координационных способностей в условиях образовательного процесса высшего учебного заведения. Анализируются принципы построения занятий, дозирования нагрузки и педагогического контроля. Обосновывается необходимость систематического применения специальных упражнений как эффективного средства укрепления здоровья, повышения работоспособности и формирования устойчивой мотивации к занятиям физической культурой.

Ключевые слова: физические качества, специальные упражнения, студенты, физическое воспитание, сила, выносливость, гибкость, координация, образовательный процесс.

INTRODUCTION

Modern conditions of study in higher education institutions are characterized by a high mental workload, limited motor activity, and an increasing incidence of functional disorders among students. Physical inactivity, stress factors, and noncompliance with work and rest schedules negatively affect the health of young people. In this regard, the issue of the purposeful development of physical qualities through physical education is particularly relevant. Physical qualities are among the most important characteristics of an individual's physical fitness. Their development contributes not only to strengthening health but also to increasing overall work capacity, enhancing resistance to adverse environmental factors, and fostering the formation of a harmoniously developed personality.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the significance of special physical exercises in the development of students' physical qualities and to substantiate methodological approaches to their application in the educational process. The main physical qualities include strength, endurance, speed, flexibility, and coordination abilities. They are interrelated and are formed through systematic motor activity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strength characterizes the ability of muscles to overcome or counteract external resistance. Endurance reflects the body's capacity to perform physical work over an extended period without a decline in efficiency. Speed is determined by the rapid execution of movements and the reaction to external stimuli. Flexibility characterizes joint mobility, while coordination abilities ensure the accuracy, consistency, and rationality of movements. The development of physical qualities in students should be based on age-related characteristics, the level of physical preparedness, and health status.

Special physical exercises occupy an important place in the system of students' physical education and represent an effective means of the purposeful development of physical qualities. Their role is determined by the possibility of selectively influencing specific functional systems of the body and particular muscle groups, thereby providing a deeper and more controlled training effect compared to general developmental exercises.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the context of modern education, characterized by high intellectual load and reduced motor activity, special exercises acquire particular significance. They help compensate for the lack of movement, prevent physical inactivity, and form an optimal level of physical preparedness among students. One of the key functions of special exercises is the development of individual physical qualities, taking into account students' individual characteristics. For example, strength-oriented exercises strengthen the muscular corset, increase the spine's resistance to static loads, and promote correct posture.

Endurance exercises improve the functioning of the cardiovascular and respiratory systems and enhance overall work capacity and resistance to fatigue. Thus, special exercises perform not only a developmental but also a preventive function by preventing functional disorders and diseases associated with a sedentary lifestyle.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

An important role of special physical exercises lies in improving neuromuscular regulation. The regular performance of purposeful motor actions leads to the formation of stable motor skills, increased movement accuracy, and enhanced coordination. This is especially relevant for students whose future professional activities may require high concentration, precision, and rapid reaction. Special exercises contribute to the formation of rational motor patterns. Properly organized classes help eliminate muscle imbalance, improve movement biomechanics, and prevent overload of individual joints and muscle groups, which is of great importance in injury prevention. The role of special exercises in fostering students' psychophysical stability is also significant. Moderate-intensity physical activity reduces stress levels, normalizes emotional state, and improves cognitive functions. During classes, such qualities as determination, discipline, perseverance, and responsibility are developed. In addition, special physical exercises allow for the individualization of the educational process. Considering the level of physical preparedness, health status, and functional capabilities of each student, the teacher can vary the intensity, volume, and orientation of the load. This approach increases the effectiveness of classes and reduces the risk of overfatigue. Special exercises also play an important role in fostering motivation for physical education. When students observe measurable improvements in physical indicators and overall well-being, they develop sustained interest in regular physical activity, which contributes to the formation of healthy lifestyle habits.

Special exercises promote the integration of theoretical knowledge and practical skills. During classes, students master the basics of self-control, learn to assess their physical condition, plan training loads, and adhere to appropriate work and rest schedules, thereby increasing their overall health culture. Thus, the role of special physical exercises in the system of students' physical education is multifaceted. They perform developmental, health-promoting, preventive, educational, and motivational functions. Their systematic and methodologically sound application ensures the harmonious development of physical qualities, strengthening of health, and increased overall work capacity of students. Strength development is an important direction of students' physical education. Strength exercises enhance the muscular corset, promote correct posture, and prevent musculoskeletal disorders. In the educational process, bodyweight exercises such as push-ups, pull-ups, and squats are applied, along with exercises using light resistance. It is important to follow the principle of gradual load progression and to consider students' individual capabilities. Strength training should be combined with stretching exercises, which help maintain joint mobility and prevent muscle overstrain. Endurance forms the basis of overall physical performance. Running, walking, aerobic elements, and circuit training are used for its development. During classes, it is necessary to monitor heart rate and gradually increase the duration of the load. The optimal effect is achieved through systematic moderate-intensity training. The development of endurance positively affects the cardiovascular and respiratory systems and increases the body's resistance to

stress. Speed and coordination play an important role in students' professional and daily activities. To develop them, reaction-speed exercises, elements of sports games, balance training, and precision movements are used. Particular attention is paid to exercise variety, which enhances neuromuscular regulation. Regular practice increases movement accuracy and reduces reaction time.

Flexibility is an important indicator of the functional state of the musculoskeletal system. Insufficient joint mobility may lead to injuries and limited motor activity. Dynamic and static stretching exercises are included in the training program and are performed after warm-up or in the final part of the session. The development of flexibility improves posture and reduces injury risk. The effectiveness of physical qualities development depends on adherence to several principles: systematic training; gradual load progression; individualization; comprehensive development of all physical qualities; and balance between load and rest. A session usually includes preparatory, main, and final parts. The preparatory part includes warm-up, the main part includes special exercises, and the final part includes relaxation exercises and breathing recovery. An important element of organizing physical education is monitoring students' physical fitness levels. For this purpose, tests assessing strength, endurance, flexibility, and speed are used. Regular monitoring allows for adjustment of the training program and individualization of the load. Evaluation of performance dynamics contributes to fostering students' motivation for physical education.

CONCLUSION

The development of physical qualities has a positive influence on the formation of willpower, discipline, and responsibility. Physical activity reduces stress levels, improves emotional well-being, and enhances self-esteem. Systematic training fosters a stable commitment to a healthy lifestyle, which is of great importance for students' future professional activities. The development of physical qualities through the use of special physical exercises is an essential component of the system of students' physical education.

A purposeful and methodologically substantiated approach to organizing classes contributes to strengthening health, increasing work capacity, and fostering a harmoniously developed personality. The comprehensive application of special exercises, consideration of individual characteristics, and regular pedagogical monitoring ensure the effectiveness of the educational process in the field of physical education.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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2026. №2(2)

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.